

Clinical performance evaluation of a novel rapid response chemiluminescent immunoassay for the detection of autoantibodies to extractable nuclear antigens

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ABSTRACT

Background: We analyzed the performance of a novel ENA screening chemiluminescent immunoassay (CIA) and the confirmation QUANTA Flash tests.

Methods: Sera (n = 1079) from patients referred to a rheumatology clinic were screened by QUANTA Flash ENA7 (INOVA Diagnostics). All positive (n = 89) and a matched control group (n = 90) were reflexed for autoantibodies to the individual antigens. Moreover, sera from patients with systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE, n = 252), systemic sclerosis (SSc, n = 64), polymyositis/dermatomyositis (PM/DM, n = 72), Sjögren's syndrome (SjS, n = 39) as well as disease controls (n = 605) were tested by ENA7 CIA and by Quanta Lite ENA6 ELISA (INOVA).

Results: 89/1079 (8.3%) samples were ENA7 CIA positive with the following reactivity profile: RNP (36.0%), Sm (13.5%), Scl-70 (9.0%), Jo-1 (0.0%), Ro60 (44.9%), Ro52 (39.3%) and SS-B (24.7%). In the negative group, the reactivity profile was: RNP (1.1%), Sm (1.1%), Scl-70 (2.2%) and 0.0% for Jo-1, Ro60, Ro52 and SS-B. The positive/negative/total agreements (ENA7 CIA vs. confirmation assays) were 95.3%/91.5%/93.3%. The sensitivity of the ENA7 CIA was 62.3% in SLE, 54.7% in SSc, 92.3% in SjS, 50.0% in PM/DM, and 61.8% in the total systemic autoimmune rheumatic disease (SARD) population (specificity 95.0%).

Conclusion: The QUANTA Flash ENA7 CIA is a reliable screening test.

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1. Introduction

Autoantibodies targeting extractable nuclear antigens (ENA) are hallmarks in the diagnosis of systemic autoimmune rheumatic diseases (SARD) such as systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) or systemic sclerosis (SSc) [1]. The primary antigenic targets of anti-ENA antibodies are U1-ribonucleoproteins (RNP), Sm (Smith antigen), Scl-70 (topoisomerase I), Jo-1, Ro60 (SS-A), Ro52 (TRIM21) and SS-B (La).

Abbreviations: ALBIA, addressable laser bead assays; AMR, analytical measuring range; CIA, chemiluminescent immunoassay; CLSI, Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute; CTD, connective tissue disease; LIA, line immunoassays; PBC, primary biliary cirrhosis; PM/DM, polymyositis/dermatomyositis; SARD, systemic autoimmune rheumatic disease; SLE, systemic lupus erythematosus; SjS, Sjögren's syndrome; SSc, systemic sclerosis.

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Not all of those antibodies are specific for a particular disease, but are useful to help ruling in or out SARD [1]. Among the disease specific antibodies, anti-Scl-70 are specific for SSc [2], anti-Jo-1 for polymyositis (PM) [1] and anti-Sm antibodies for SLE [1,3]. Among the most common antibodies are antibodies to Ro52, Ro60 and SS-B which therefore deserve special attention and careful evaluation. Historically, anti-Ro52 and anti-Ro60 antibodies have been detected and reported simultaneously. However, recent data suggested that both the cellular function and the clinical association of anti-Ro52 and anti-Ro60 antibodies are significantly different [4]. Anti-Ro60 antibodies are associated with SLE and SjS whereas anti-Ro52 antibodies can be found in various disease conditions including PM and SSc [5] but also in several forms of lung disease associated with autoimmunity [6]. Of high importance, about 20% of anti-Ro52/anti-Ro60 antibodies can be missed when tested using a blend of the two antigens [4]. Besides the diagnostic value of antibodies to Ro52, Ro60 and SS-B, it has been shown that those antibody specificities can precede the clinical onset of SLE for many years [7]. In addition to SARD, previous studies have reported autoantibodies to ENA in PBC [1,8]. Several methods have been developed and used for the detection of anti-ENA antibodies

including ELISA, line immunoassays (LIA) [9], addressable laser bead assays (ALBIA) [10–13] and protein arrays [14]. During the last years, the chemiluminescence technology, which has been used for clinical chemistry for a long time, has been applied for autoantibody testing [15].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sera

Sera ($n = 1079$) from patients referred to a rheumatology clinic were screened for anti-ENA7 antibodies by QUANTA Flash ENA7 (INOVA Diagnostics, Inc., San Diego, CA). All positive samples ($n = 89$) and approximately the same number of randomly selected negative samples ($n = 90$) were reflexed for autoantibodies to the individual antigens (RNP, Sm, Scl-70, Jo-1, Ro60, Ro52 and SS-B) using the QUANTA Flash assays. To compare the clinical performance of the QUANTA Flash ENA7 CIA to a predicate device, sera from patients with SLE ($n = 252$), SSC ($n = 64$), PM/DM ($n = 72$), and SjS ($n = 39$), as well as various disease controls ($n = 605$, for details see the Results section) were tested by QUANTA Flash ENA7 CIA and by Quanta Lite ENA6 ELISA (INOVA; RNP, Sm, Scl-70, Jo-1, Ro60, Ro52 and SS-B). Additionally, sera from patients with PBC ($n = 52$) were screened by both methods, but were not included as part of the disease controls for analysis since PBC patients are known to have ENAs. A list of the disease cohorts and controls can be found in the Results section. To verify the specificity of the Scl-70 assay, various disease controls were tested ($n = 628$). The diagnoses were established as described before [3] or according to the standard disease criteria.

This study meets and is in compliance with all ethical standards in medicine. Patient identity was not disclosed and the data was anonymously used in accordance with the latest version of the Helsinki Declaration of human research ethics.

2.2. QUANTA Flash^(R) assays

The QUANTA Flash assays (INOVA Diagnostics Inc., San Diego, CA) are novel CIA that are currently used on the Bio-Flash® instrument (Biokit s.a., Barcelona, Spain), a fully automated chemiluminescent immuno-analyzer. The principle of the Bio-Flash system has recently been described [15]. The QUANTA Flash assays used in this study were developed using native or recombinant antigens (INOVA Diagnostics, see Table 1) coated onto paramagnetic beads. Prior to use, the lyophilized beads are resuspended using the resuspension buffer. A patient serum sample is pre-diluted with the Bio-Flash® sample buffer in a small disposable plastic cuvette. Small amounts of the diluted patient serum, the beads, and the assay buffer are all combined into a second cuvette, mixed, and then incubated for 9.5 min at 37 °C. The magnetized beads are sedimented using a strong magnet in the washing station and washed several times followed by addition of isoluminol conjugated anti-human IgG and again incubated 9.5 min at 37 °C. The magnetized beads are sedimented and washed repeatedly. The isoluminol conjugate is oxidized when sodium hydroxide solution and peroxide solutions (“triggers”) are added to the cuvette, and the flash of light produced from this reaction is measured as relative light units (RLUs) by the Bio-Flash® optical system. The RLUs are proportional to the amount of isoluminol conjugate that is

bound to the human IgG, which is in turn proportional to the amount of autoantibodies bound to the antigen on the beads. The Bio-Flash system also allows the customer the option to reflex the individual assays of a screening test such as the QUANTA Flash ENA7.

2.3. Quanta Lite assays

Quanta Lite ENA6 was used as a comparator method. This ELISA contains the same number of antigens as the QUANTA Flash ENA7. Historically, Ro52 and Ro60 were called SS-A [4] and therefore counted as one antigen when the Quanta Lite ENA6 was developed. The antigen composition and sources are shown in Table 1. The assay was performed according to the direction of use.

2.4. Precision and linearity studies

Precision and linearity of the assays were verified by performing the required testing according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines. For the precision study, the within run, between day, between run, and total precision were determined by running 2 aliquots of the precision samples twice a day in random order, with a minimum of 2 h between each run. The samples were run on the same instrument for each assay and repeated for at least 20 days, according to CLSI guideline EP5-A2. Linearity testing was performed according to CLSI guideline EP6-A (Vol. 23, No. 16), which involved diluting several high titer sera in a serial dilution scheme to span the analytical measuring range (AMR) for each assay.

2.5. Generation of mono-specific samples (Jo-1)

Seven samples with high titers of Jo-1 antibodies were diluted in normal serum to yield negative or low positive results for all other autoantibodies to antigens contained in the ENA7 Screen. Those samples were then used to analyze the sensitivity of QUANTA Flash ENA7 for Jo-1.

2.6. Statistical analyses

The data were statistically evaluated using the Analyse-it Software (ver 1.62; Analyse-it Software, Ltd., Leeds, UK). Linearity results were analyzed by linear regression analysis, and slope, intercept and R² values were calculated. Chi-square, Spearman's correlation and Cohen's kappa agreement tests were carried out to analyze the agreement between portions and $p < 0.05$ was considered significant. Receiver-operating characteristics (ROC) analysis was used to analyze the discriminatory ability of different immunoassays.

3. Results

3.1. Precision and linearity

Precision study results for all QUANTA Flash CIAs are shown in Table 2. The total precision for all assays varied between 3.8 and 13.8%. The linearity study results are tabulated in Table 3 for all QUANTA Flash CIA assays. All assays demonstrated linearity over the AMR.

Table 1
Antigen composition of QUANTA Flash ENA7 and QUANTA Lite ENA6.

Antigen	QUANTA Flash ENA7	QUANTA Lite ENA6
RNP	Native purified	Native purified
Sm	Native purified	Native purified
SS-A Ro60	Recombinant, insect cells	Native purified
SS-B La	Recombinant, insect cells	Native purified
Ro52	Recombinant, insect cells	Recombinant, insect cells
Scl-70	Recombinant, insect cells	Native purified
Jo-1	Recombinant, insect cells	Native purified

Table 2
Precision data of the QUANTA Flash CIA assays.

	No. of samples	Within run	Between-day	Between-run	Total
ENA7	8	1.8–4.3%	2.6–6.3%	0.0–2.6%	4.0–7.1%
RNP	7	3.4–4.8%	3.0–9.3%	0.0–4.5%	4.8–10.8%
Sm	5	5.3–9.7%	2.7–5.8%	0.5–7.1%	8.3–11.5%
Ro60	9	2.9–5.8%	0.0–2.6%	2.9–9.6%	3.8–10.5%
Ro52	6	4.1–6.9%	6.2–11.6%	0.0–4.1%	9.8–12.5%
SS-B	7	3.7–9.3%	7.2–9.9%	1.8–6.8%	9.7–13.8%
Scl-70	7	2.2–4.5%	0.0–2.6%	1.9–4.2%	4.3–5.0%
Jo-1	9	2.9–5.0%	4.7–6.8%	0.0–3.0%	6.2–8.0%

Table 3
Linearity data of the QUANTA Flash CIAs.

Assay	AMR (CU)	Test range (CU)	Slope (95% CI)	Y-intercept (95% CI)	R ²	Percent recovery
ENA7	3.6–429.4	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
RNP	3.5–643.8	3.8 to 649.0	1.00 (1.00 to 1.01)	−4.28 (−7.14 to −1.42)	1.00	85.0–109.4% ^a
Sm	3.3–693.5	3.3 to 742.6	1.00 (0.98 to 1.01)	0.02 (−3.98 to 4.02)	0.99	88.0–112.8%
Ro60	4.9–1374.8	3.9 to 1370.1	1.00 (0.98 to 1.10)	1.69 (−4.58 to 7.95)	1.00	89.4–109.0%
Ro52	2.3–1685.3	0.6 to 1758.6	1.03 (1.02 to 1.04)	3.61 (−0.86 to 8.08)	1.00	94.7–118.4% ^a
SS-B	3.3–1706.8	3.4 to 1828.1	1.03 (1.01 to 1.04)	3.44 (−2.72 to 9.60)	0.99	91.3–119.6% ^a
Scl-70	3.8–969.8	2.1 to 1476.0	1.03 (1.02 to 1.03)	−1.29 (−4.78 to 2.19)	1.00	90.3–118.9%
Jo-1	2.2–1147.2	1.4 to 1203.6	0.99 (0.99 to 1.00)	−2.23 (−4.43 to −0.03)	1.00	89.9–118.0%

NA = not applicable since qualitative assay; AMR = analytical measuring range.

^a Or less than 2 units difference.

3.2. Referral cohort

A total of 89/1079 (8.3%) samples were positive by QUANTA Flash ENA7 CIA (Fig. 1). Of those, the prevalence of autoantibodies to the individual antigens was: RNP (36.0%), Sm (13.5%), Scl-70 (9.0%), Jo-1 (0.0%), Ro60 (44.9%), Ro52 (39.3%) and SS-B (24.7%) (Fig. 2). In the QUANTA Flash ENA7 CIA negative group, the prevalence of autoantibodies to the individual antigens was: RNP (1.1%), Sm (1.1%), Scl-70 (2.2%), Jo-1 (0.0%), Ro60 (0.0%), Ro52 (0.0%) and SS-B (0.0%). The positive, negative and total agreement between the QUANTA Flash ENA7 Screen and the QUANTA Flash confirmation assays were 95.3%, 91.5% and 93.3%, respectively. All four QUANTA Flash ENA7 negative, confirmation assay positive samples were negative by ELISA. Since the two ENA7 negative Scl-70 positive patients had no evidence of SSc (analyzed by chart review; one patient had a diagnosis of psoriatic arthritis, HLA B27-negative; the other patient had ankylosing spondylitis with peripheral joint involvement and Psoriasis, HLA B27-positive), we

screened various disease cohorts for anti-Scl-70 antibodies and found a specificity of 98.7% (Fig. 3).

3.3. Disease cohorts

A summary of the disease cohorts and the prevalence of ENA autoantibodies using both assay methods can be found in Table 4. In the clinically defined disease cohorts, the sensitivities of QUANTA Flash ENA7 CIA/Quanta Lite ENA6 ELISA were 62.3%/61.5% for SLE, 54.7%/57.8% for SSc, 50.0%/55.6% for PM/DM, 92.3%/89.7% for SjS and 61.8%/62.5% for SARD combined, respectively. Screening of sera from PBC patients resulted in 19.2%/11.5% prevalence for the ENA7 CIA and ENA6 ELISA, respectively. The specificities were 95.0% for QUANTA Flash and 93.7% for Quanta Lite. Receiver operating characteristic analysis for QUANTA Flash ENA7 CIA/Quanta Lite ENA6 ELISA showed area under the curve values of 0.866/0.877 (SLE vs. controls), 0.812/0.871 (SSc vs. controls), 0.750/

Fig. 1. Referral study. A total of 1079 samples were screened for anti-ENA antibodies by Quanta Flash ENA7. The positive ($n = 89$) and approximately the same number of negative samples ($n = 90$) were tested for the individual antibodies. In 8 of the positive samples no individual specificity could be found. Vice versa, 4 of the ENA negative samples showed reactivity to at least on individual component.

Fig. 2. Prevalence a.) and titers b.) of anti-ENA antibodies in Quanta Flash ENA7 Screen positive ($n = 89$) and negative samples ($n = 90$). Results for antibodies to Sm, RNP, Ro60, Ro52, SS-B, Scl-70 and Jo-1 in relation to the ENA7 results are shown.

0.798 (PM/DM vs. controls), 0.966/0.967 (SjS vs. controls), 0.617/0.562 (PBC vs. controls), and 0.847/0.871 (SARD vs. controls), respectively.

3.4. Validation of QUANTA Flash ENA7 for Jo-1

Since anti-Jo-1 antibodies are rare our referral cohort did not include any Jo-1 positive sample. Therefore we studied the performance for anti-Jo-1 antibodies using mono-specific samples. Seven samples with high titer anti-Jo-1 antibodies were diluted in normal serum and tested on the ENA7 and for the individual antibodies. Two out of the seven samples were mono-specific for anti-Jo-1 antibodies (with low titers) and yielded positive results using the ENA7 screen (66.0 CU and 67.3 CU). The five remaining samples showed reactivity not only to Jo-1, but also to Ro52 as expected [16] and were highly positive using the ENA7 screen (85.9 CU, 110.9 CU, 109.2 CU, 234.1 CU and 148.3 CU).

4. Discussion

The detection of anti-ENA antibodies is important to help in the diagnosis of SARD [1]. In recent years, several new methods for the detection of anti-ENA antibodies have been developed and commercialized with special focus on automation and ease of use [17]. However, since reliable detection of autoantibodies should still be the most desirable goal, careful verification and validation of the assay performance are mandatory. Consequently, we undertook this study

to analyze the performance characteristics of QUANTA Flash ENA7 and the confirmation assays.

In our referral cohort, we found a good agreement between the QUANTA Flash ENA7 and the confirmatory assays (93.3%). It is desirable that screening assays are more sensitive than confirmatory tests. In keeping with this concept, we found eight ENA7 screen positive, but confirmatory assay negative specimens. Only four samples that were negative on the screening test showed reactivity to at least one of the individual antigens and all of them had very low titers. This demonstrates that the QUANTA Flash ENA7 efficiently detects almost all antibodies. However, based on the absence of anti-Jo-1 antibodies in our referral cohort, further studies are needed to analyze the agreement for Jo-1.

Although the ENA7 CIA and the ENA6 ELISA use different sources of antigens (recombinant vs. native for Ro60, SS-B, Scl-70), the results are very similar. During the last decade, significant improvements have been made in recombinant protein technology [18]. Especially novel strategies for the generation of recombinant Ro60 led to the availability of this antigen as a recombinant protein [4]. Recombinant antigen manufacturing is more consistent and less dependent on the biological variations of the source material. Based on the advances, recombinant proteins were the preferred source of antigens for the development of the novel ENA7 screen. Therefore, the novel CIA shows similar assay performance combined with higher degree of consistency.

Fig. 3. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis. ROC curves are shown for SARD a.), SLE b.), SSc c.), SJS d.), PM/DM e.), and PBC f.). Arrows indicate the cut-off values of CIA and ELISA. The sensitivity and specificity of the CIA and the ELISA are similar in SARD (n = 427), SLE (n = 252), SSc (n = 64), SJS (n = 39), and PM/DM (n = 72).

Recently it was demonstrated that the Quanta Lite ENA6 Screen ELISA shows similar sensitivity, but much higher specificity compared to ANA on HEp-2 in a large tertiary hospital reference laboratory [19]. In addition, apparent shifts in referral patterns away from specialists [20] are increasing the inappropriate ordering and interpretation of ANA testing [21].

Since we found 2 patients with anti-Scl-70 antibodies without evidence of SSc we screened a large population of controls and found high specificity, higher than previously reported in a meta-analysis [2]. Several studies have nicely shown the presence of autoantibodies before the clinical onset of SARD [22]. Some studies also reported the evolution of SSc in patients initially diagnosed with primary SjS [23].

Whether the anti-Scl-70 antibodies in those patients have clinical relevance remains unclear.

Several studies have demonstrated limited sensitivity [24–26] and specificity [12,27,28,28,29], of IIF on HEp-2 cells. Especially for anti-Rib-P and anti-Ro antibodies, the IIF has been reported to lack reliability [20,24–26]. In a comparative analysis of an ANA ELISA and ANA IIF, equivalent sensitivity and specificity of the two methods were observed [28]. Several studies have reported ANA negative SLE [30,31]. In a study by Davis et al., 39 ANA negative patients with detectable levels of ENA have been retrospectively investigated and the majority of the patients were diagnosed as having CTD [32]. It was found that adding of antigen specific assays

Table 4
Prevalence of autoantibodies in different disease cohorts.

Cohort	n =	ENA7 CIA No (%) pos	ENA6 ELISA No (%) pos
Systemic autoimmune rheumatic diseases	427	264 (61.8%)	267 (62.5%)
Systemic lupus erythematosus	252	157 (62.3%)	155 (61.5%)
Systemic sclerosis	64	35 (54.7%)	37 (57.8%)
Sjögren's syndrome	39	36 (92.3%)	35 (89.7%)
Polymyositis/dermatomyositis	72	36 (50.0%)	40 (55.6%)
Other diseases	605	30 (5.0%)	38 (6.3%)
Ankylosing spondylitis	13	1 (7.7%)	0 (0.0%)
Celiac disease	43	2 (4.7%)	3 (7.0%)
Degenerative spine disease	6	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Fibromyalgia	5	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Osteoarthritis	50	2 (4.0%)	3 (6.0%)
Rheumatoid arthritis	132	10 (7.6%)	9 (6.8%)
Inflammatory bowel disease	50	4 (8.0%)	4 (8.0%)
Hepatitis C virus	24	0 (0.0%)	7 (29.1%)
Hepatitis B virus	16	0 (0.0%)	1 (6.3%)
Human immunodeficiency virus	7	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Syphilis	6	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Polymyalgia rheumatica	21	0 (0.0%)	1 (4.8%)
Psoriasis arthritis	14	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Others	20	1 (5.0%)	1 (5.0%)
Vasculitis	2	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Healthy individuals	196	10 (5.1%)	9 (4.6%)
Primary biliary cirrhosis	52	10 (19.2%)	6 (11.5%)

to IIF on HEp-2 cells significantly improves the diagnostic algorithm for the diagnosis of SARD [33]. However, it was concluded in this study that changing from IIF to other methods for ANA detection also requires modification of the disease criteria. In addition, it was highly recommended to use anti-Ro assays in addition to IIF [33].

During the last 20 years several multiplex technologies have been developed and used in laboratory medicine [10,34]. Among the earliest assays, line-immunoassays (LIA) can basically be considered as second generation dot-blot assays. A broad range of LIAs are commercially available and they are usually used to confirm previous identified autoantibodies. However, those assays might also have been considered as a screening test for ANA or ENA [35]. Mainly manually performed, these assays offer a simple way of multiplex testing and even automated LIAs have become available [9]. Multiplex assays based on the Luminex technology use addressable laser beads and are therefore often referred to as ALBIA (addressable laser bead assays) [34]. Today several commercial ALBIA kits are available for the detection of autoantibodies to nuclear antigens [11–13,29,36–40]. Similar to LIAs, the number of antigens and the antigen composition significantly vary. Multiplex assays are commonly used as a screening test for anti-ENA/ANA or other autoantibodies. Usually the cost per antibody test for those assays is lower compared to single analyte testing, but more expensive than screening assays using a blend of different antigens. Since most samples sent to a laboratory are negative [21] (consistent with our data; >90% were negative), screening assays are mostly more cost-effective than multiplexing as screening assays. This might be different in laboratories specialized in immunology with high percentages of sample referrals from rheumatologists and therefore with high positive rate.

More than 70% of anti-Jo-1 positive patients are also positive for anti-Ro52. Besides anti-Ro52 antibodies, PM patients also have other antibodies [4,16]. Thus the probability is <20% that anti-Jo-1 positive patients, i.e., 4% of all myositis patients are monospecific. Therefore mono-specific samples had to be created to validate the QUANTA Flash ENA7 CIA. Using this approach it has been demonstrated that the ENA7 CIA detects even low levels of anti-Jo-1 antibodies and is therefore a reliable screening test for autoantibodies to all antigens contained in the Screen.

Some studies reported antibodies to ENA in patients with PBC, especially autoantibodies to antibodies Ro52 [8]. Based on these

findings, we analyzed the utility of the ENA Screening assays for the differentiation between PBC patients and controls. Although the discrimination between the 2 groups was better using the QUANTA Flash assay, anti-ENA antibodies in general might add significant information to support the diagnosis of PBC. However, considering the small number of patients and the low prevalence of anti-ENA antibodies in PBC we acknowledge a limitation of this part of the study. Further studies with large cohorts of PBC patients are necessary to carefully evaluate the clinical utility of the ENA Screen for PBC.

5. Conclusion

Our data demonstrate that QUANTA Flash ENA7 is a reliable screening test for the rapid detection (30 min) of antibodies to RNP, Sm, Ro60, Ro52, SS-B, Scl-70 and Jo-1. Using the reflex function of the software, samples positive for anti-ENA antibodies can be reflexed and tested for reactivity against the individual antigens.

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